

REPORT

Open Access Books Usage Data Trust Environmental Scan

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Developing a Pilot Data Trust for Open Access Ebook Usage Project

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1 Introduction

The Exploring Open Access eBook Usage (OAeBU) project is a pilot initiative aiming to create and manage an international data trust which will facilitate data sharing among different stakeholders in the publication of OA ebooks. Potential stakeholders in the trust include providers throughout the books supply chain, including commercial publishers, university presses, scholarly societies, libraries, ebook hosting platforms, aggregators, standards bodies, and other participants in the scholarly publishing ecosystem. Because these stakeholders might have divergent and potentially conflicting interests, the data trust will provide a neutral and cooperative framework to allow aggregation, standardization, and accessibility of data about OA ebooks, while respecting ethical norms in the use of metrics.

Clarke & Esposito was engaged to develop a map of the supply chain for OA monographs to illustrate the many categories and relationships of stakeholders that might be served by this initiative, and to identify the gaps (and opportunities) in information exchange.¹ Based on the ecosystem described in that map, the project team engaged C&E to explore the following questions:

- Are there any entities who may be positioned to host the envisioned OA book usage data exchange for both public and private parties (either with or without an accompanying data analytics service)?
- Are there any providers who could offer partnership opportunities with OAeBU and the data trust, based on alignment with stakeholders, key principles, mission, and governance structure?
- Are there any providers who are currently positioned to create a direct competitor to the prototype OAeBU data dashboard?

To answer, C&E conducted an environmental scan to identify and examine providers based on their aims and alignment with the stated goals of the OAeBU project.

2 Methodology

The environmental scan included desk research across publicly available sources including provider websites, public announcements and press releases, blog posts, and other industry publications. Where available, we also incorporated findings from research interviews conducted during our previous analysis of the OA monographs supply chain.

¹ For the complete findings from our supply chain analysis, see the “OA Monographs Supply Chain Mapping Report”, available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681725>

During our review, we identified a short list of twelve providers which present the greatest opportunity for collaboration – or competition – with the OAeBU initiative. We provided a full profile and assessment for each of these providers in **Section 4** of this report.

In the report’s **Appendix**, we have included brief profiles for another twelve providers covered in our environmental scan, where we found only indirect overlap. These represent providers which the OAeBU project team might monitor and perhaps engage with, but which (in the view of C&E) are not well positioned for direct collaboration, hosting, or competition with the data trust.

This version of the report reflects C&E’s preliminary findings, which are intended to inform OAeBU principal investigators and the project team in anticipation of exploratory conversations with certain providers. Results of those conversations will be incorporated into a later, final version of this report.

3 Summary of Preliminary Findings

Our review encompassed a diverse list of providers and sought to understand the potential vectors of both cooperation and competition. We defined the organizations with the most affinity for potential collaboration or leadership of the data trust as those cross-industry data collaboratives/exchanges where there is clear overlap with OAeBU stakeholders, mission, and focus. For example, collaborative initiatives serving multiple parts of the OA books supply chain share a similar mission as OAeBU, and we deemed them most likely of the providers in our environmental scan to be able to provide future support in some form. We also noted where these organizations gather usage or other data from multiple competing parties, which could provide a template for OAeBU.

We also identified several organizations with strong overlap where there was *potential* conflict in the provider’s ability to act as a central, neutral administrator for the OAeBU data exchange. In the context of this environmental scan, “neutrality” refers to an organization’s ability to administer the trust without the *perception* of favoring one participant over another. An organization might be “conflicted” (meaning, unable to appear neutral) if they play an important role in some part of the supply chain which would put them in competition with other participants of the data trust – regardless of that organization’s actual handling of the data, there is the *potential* it could use its position to its own advantage, so the market would not perceive that organization as neutral.

We defined “directly competitive” providers as those which serve similar stakeholders, and offer a similar usage data aggregation service. These providers are “competitive” in that they reduce their customers’ need for an industry-wide data exchange like OAeBU. Their interests in offering a proprietary exchange also provide a disincentive to support an open, community-based data exchange.

We also observed some providers who fell in the middle of the competitive vs. cooperative spectrum, for example community initiatives with some overlap with OAeBU aims and scope, with a focus on only a certain type of stakeholder. These latter providers were deemed “opportunities for collaboration”, as they may already have some infrastructure in place to address similar problems to the OAeBU data trust, and may act as stakeholders or contributors in their own right to the data exchange.

Our review also noted examples where the OAeBU data trust might provide an opportunity to serve stakeholders outside of the OA books supply chain – for example, expanding its services to the paid access books supply chain, or to OA journals. As we found in our supply chain research, OA books have their own unique needs and their success will require standards and best practices that are fit for purpose (rather than repurposed from OA journals, or retrofit to paid access book systems). However, the problems addressed by the OAeBU data trust are shared by other content types and models, so we have noted where the project team might explore some of these opportunities in the long term.

What follows is a brief description of how we categorized the most relevant providers, based on the findings detailed in our environmental scan profiles.

3.1 Cross-Industry Data Collaboratives and Exchanges

We found only a few examples of initiatives working to consolidate usage data across multiple platform types. Of these, only two (**OpenAIRE Usage Statistics** and **Crossref’s Distributed Usage Logging** project) operate (or operated) as neutrally administered participatory initiatives working across many (in several cases competing) stakeholders. OpenAIRE collects usage data from several repositories, aggregators and platforms for display in the OpenAIRE Research Graph. Unlike the OAeBU initiative, OpenAIRE’s scope is limited to EU research, and considers multiple content types (of which OA monographs are only a subset). Crossref’s support for Distributed Usage Logging (in collaboration with Project COUNTER) indicates that they have the ability and influence to convene initiatives which build consensus around sharing usage data across platforms. However, there is a question of mission alignment: Crossref voted to transfer

their ownership of the Distributed Usage Logging project in November 2020 (it is still looking for a successor organization).

CHORUS and the **OA Switchboard** are other examples of initiatives establishing a secure, neutral data exchange, but their purview is currently focused on compliance-based, not performance-based, reporting metrics. In other words, their current role is to confirm that articles are published and paid for in accordance with open access funder mandates. Engagement with usage data, as in the OAeBU data trust, would be a significant expansion of their current role.

Standards bodies, such as **NISO** and **Project COUNTER**, provide the broadest international venue for neutral and cross-industry organization, and each has provided support for initiatives to convene stakeholders in the books supply chain (both traditional and OA). Their typical role in such initiatives is that of organizer or convener; currently, neither is equipped to support hosting or implementation.

3.2 Other Potential Collaborators

The **OAPEN Foundation** is aligned with the OAeBU mission of establishing new industry best practices and standards for OA monographs. Because they collect metadata and offer cross-platform discovery for the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) index, they have the right stakeholder relationships in place to collect usage data. However, because OAPEN also operates a platform (the OAPEN Library), they would also be a contributor to the usage data trust – as would OAPEN Library’s competitors, which could affect OAPEN’s ability to serve as a neutral administrator.

For participants in the **Sustainable History Monographs Publishing (SHMP)** pilot, Longleaf Services (a nonprofit university press book distributor) offers consolidated usage reporting as part of its exploration of the role of an “OA distributor”. Though the SHMP pilot itself is designed as a collaborative industry effort, its administration of data sharing happens via a traditional distributor which competes with other OA and traditional distributors, and is affiliated with a participating university press. Though SHMP, like the OAPEN Foundation, is well-aligned with the goals and mission of OAeBU, and is even doing preliminary work to explore its central question, there are operational and organizational reasons why they may not be perceived as a neutral party able to expand these activities as administrators of an industry-wide data trust.

3.3 Potential Competitors

Knowledge Unlatched Open Analytics was the one example we found of a provider within the OA books supply chain which currently collects and consolidates usage reports to illustrate the impact of OA titles. While KU and OAeBU both aim to support sustainable and global Open Access models, KU's open analytics service primarily acts as business development for KU's funding and distribution activities. KU's role cannot be described as neutral for two reasons: first, given its simultaneous role as a funder, distributor, and platform, other stakeholders in the data trust may consider KU a competitor (as with our examples of "conflicted" providers, above). Second, as KU fills the need among its customers for the collection and aggregation of usage across platforms, it reduces their need for a similar data trust from OAeBU. This is the most directly competitive initiative to the OAeBU data trust.

3.4 Narrower Collaboration Opportunities

There are several initiatives which successfully collect and consolidate usage data across platforms and share similar goals with OAeBU, but which focus on the interests of only a small part of the OA books supply chain. For example, the **IRUS Network** and **Repository Analytics and Metrics Portal (RAMP)** each only collect usage metrics for institutional repositories. The **Toward an Open Monographs Ecosystem (TOME)** initiative explores OA funding methods and tracks performance, but only for a small group of participating university press publishers. It is unlikely these services would be directly competitive, and they may in fact be good collaborators with OAeBU in areas of mutual interest.

3.5 Other Providers

Our environmental scan included many other organizations and initiatives which draw information from multiple sources and aim to improve evaluation of different types of content (both OA and otherwise). Several of these had only limited overlap with OA monographs stakeholders; others were focused on other types of data beyond usage; still others were commercial providers focused on products with little mission overlap with OAeBU. As these providers fall into the further reaches of the ecosystem, we deemed both the collaborative and competitive potential more limited and profiled them more briefly.

4 Provider Profiles

This section provides extended profiles and analysis of the providers which C&E determined have the most stakeholder overlap and alignment with the OAeBU initiative. A list of these providers, and C&E’s assessment of the potential collaborative or competitive opportunity for OAeBU, is provided in the table below.

C&E Assessment of OAeBU Opportunity	Provider
Cross-Industry Data Exchange	CHORUS
	Crossref
	National Information Standards Organization (NISO)
	OA Switchboard
	OpenAIRE Usage Statistics
Other Potential Collaborator	OAPEN Foundation
	Sustainable History Monograph Pilot (SHMP)
Potential Competitor	Knowledge Unlatched Open Analytics
Narrower Collaboration Opportunity	IRUS Network
	Repository Analytics and Metrics Portal (RAMP)
	Toward an Open Monograph Ecosystem (TOME)

Additional brief profiles of providers we reviewed and found only indirect competition or collaboration opportunity are included in the report’s **Appendix**.

4.1 Cross-Industry Data Collaboratives and Exchanges

CHORUS

<https://www.chorusaccess.org/>

Profile

CHORUS is a membership organization which aims to develop solutions for tracking the open access status of content and datasets which report on funded research.

Legal Status

CHOR, Inc. is a US 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization.

Key Stakeholders:

- CHORUS membership includes **publishers, funders, technology and resource partners**, and other organizations engaged in scholarly publishing.
- Currently CHORUS has ~40 publisher members, including several of the large commercial publishers, societies, and two university presses.
- CHORUS was launched following the issuance of the US Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) February 2013 directive requiring a maximum 12-month green OA embargo for US-funded research. This gives the organization a strong US focus, although they also support compliance monitoring for select non-US funders (e.g., the Japan Science and Technology Agency).

Related Activities:

- CHORUS compiles and reports information about the OA status of articles and their connection to a particular funder (as indicated in article metadata and compared to the Crossref Open Funder Registry). It provides this information via a search service (currently in beta), reporting dashboards, and a set of public APIs for funders.
- CHORUS offers dashboards which report on key compliance indicators for OA funding and access mandates – for example, whether an article is made open access (and via what model), whether appropriate reuse terms are available, if datasets are included alongside the article, and so on. Dashboards can be customized for a particular funder by request, to provide an overview of overall compliance and publication trends.

Operational and Technical Structure

- CHORUS is governed by its members, who serve on a largely volunteer basis on its Board of Directors, Committees, and Working Groups. CHORUS is managed by a full-time Executive Director.
- CHORUS aims for its infrastructure to build on proven systems, rather than requiring agencies and providers to establish new services. It receives significant technical support from Crossref, which maintains and freely contributes the Crossref Open Funder Registry and plays a key advisory role in CHORUS development and governance.

CHORUS's use of the Open Funder Registry was also supported by an initial donation from Elsevier of its taxonomy of international funder names and IDs.

Key Principles

- Community and member-driven.
- Providing the metadata infrastructure for smooth, low-friction exchange of information.
- Improving OA availability by minimizing the burden for compliance.
- Increasing access to literature in support of global funder mandates.

C&E Analysis

CHORUS was launched in 2013 to address a need by US funding agencies to monitor the impact of a newly-enacted OA mandate. The breadth of the mandate's impact provided a strong incentive for publishers to support the initiative. CHORUS's emphasis on re-using existing infrastructure also made it easy for its services to gain traction, by minimizing the requirements for technological change and workflow redesign. Its ability to provide a forum for collaboration between erstwhile competitors (in this case publishers) to share data on OA publication – including for books – could be instructional for OAeBU.

Beyond its role as a collaborative data exchange, the aims and scope of CHORUS may not provide much additional overlap with those of OAeBU. CHORUS services are DOI-based, so books are included in its reports, but the language in its reporting suggests a focus on journal articles and (more recently) data sets. (For example, instructions prominently displayed on the dashboard invite users to “click through to DOI links to journal articles on publishers’ sites”.) Its journals focus is also reflected in its membership: most CHORUS members are focused on journals publishing, with very little representation from SSH or University Press providers. CHORUS has little incentive to expand its services for books without the presence of funder mandates specifically pertaining to this format.

More importantly, CHORUS's information exchange does not consider usage – the dashboard is completely silent on the *performance* or *evaluation* of OA content. This may be partly because some CHORUS members produce their own commercial products to track citations and provide quality metrics, and would not support CHORUS's evolution into a competitive product. CHORUS instead focuses only on *compliance*. Introducing a new performance-based metric like usage could be politically charged for CHORUS and its members, and may be the real limiter of its ability to handle the kind of data envisioned by OAeBU.

Crossref

<https://www.crossref.org/>

Profile

Crossref is a membership organization that “exists to make scholarly communications better”. Their main activity is as a registry for Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and for providing related services to enable content discovery, citation, linking, assessment, and reuse.

Legal Status

Crossref is a US 501(c)(6) nonprofit organization.

Key Stakeholders:

- Membership in Crossref is primarily for organizations that produce scholarly content (e.g., **publishers**).
- Other organizations with an interest in Crossref activities can be members, such as **research institutions, government agencies, research funders, and technology partners**.

Related Activities:

- Crossref is a common source of DOIs for journal articles, books, book chapters, and other scholarly content types, and provides regular reporting to publishers about DOI resolutions for their content.
- Because ebooks are available on multiple platforms and some may have multiple competing DOIs, Crossref has attempted to improve access across platforms in two ways: Multiple Resolution, which allows a single DOI to resolve to multiple platforms, and Co-access, which consolidates information about a single title with multiple DOIs. In research interviews with C&E, Crossref signaled that both solutions leave room for improvement, but updates are behind other items on the roadmap. (Issues related to DOIs in OA monographs were covered in detail in C&E’s supply chain mapping report.)
- In partnership with Project COUNTER, Crossref supported the Distributed Usage Logging initiative from 2017 to 2020, which was intended to help publishers capture usage of their content across multiple sites, and explored a peer-to-peer channel for the secure exchange of COUNTER-compliant, anonymized usage records from hosting platforms to publishers. In November 2020, the Crossref Board made a decision to transfer ownership of the initiative to another organization. As of April 2021, no successor organization has been named.

Operational and Technical Structure

- Crossref is a community-focused organization governed by its membership, and is transparent about its strategic roadmap and initiatives. (An example of its 2020 strategic roadmap is visible here: <https://www.crossref.org/strategy/>)

- Crossref itself offers various tools and services to structure and process metadata, but also provides guidance around the standards and best practices its members are expected to follow.
- Crossref is active in the development of new infrastructure, through collaboration, incubation, or by development of a new Crossref service. Initiatives such as ORCID and the Research Organization Registry (ROR) are now independent, but were originally launched as Crossref initiatives.

Key Principles

- Community and member-driven.
- Access model neutral (meaning, Crossref supports both OA and paid access models).
- In December 2020, Crossref adopted the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) as a sign of its commitment to transparency and neutrality.²

C&E Analysis

Crossref is a trusted and transparent intermediary for stakeholders throughout scholarly publishing, and has taken concrete steps to protect their role as a neutral player. They have pre-existing relationships with many of the stakeholders across the OA monographs ecosystem (particularly publishers and platform providers, where Crossref currently provides a bridge for DOI resolution reporting). They also have a history of supporting community initiatives, at times working in collaboration with other standards bodies such as Project COUNTER. The Distributed Usage Logging project is a concrete example of how it has successfully convened stakeholders to provide a more open exchange of usage data – an effort which parallels those of the OAeBU data trust.

There are two potential barriers to explore around Crossref’s future role in supporting the OAeBU data trust: first, Crossref membership is not as strong among books publishers as it is in among journals publishers (the DOI is a less common identifier than the ISBN, and there is room for improvement of its services for books). Because of the unique requirements of book publishers and providers, Crossref’s existing infrastructure might require additional development to address these complexities. If OAeBU is able to meet its goals for OA monographs, Crossref may provide more opportunities for applying key lessons to other content types, particularly journals or datasets where use of the DOI better established.

This leads to the second potential barrier: mission alignment. Crossref has recently stepped away from the Distributed Usage Logging initiative after three years of support. Crossref’s reasoning for transitioning ownership of this project to another organization is worth exploring, as it may inform their willingness to engage with OAeBU.

² For a list of these principles, see “The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure”, available at this link: <https://doi.org/10.24343/C34W2H>

National Information Standards Organization (NISO)

<http://www.niso.org/>

Profile

NISO is an industry-based, nonprofit, non-governmental association. NISO is accredited by the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) to identify, develop, maintain, and publish voluntary, consensus-based standards for managing information.

Legal Status

NISO is a US 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization.

Key Stakeholders:

- NISO supports standards and recommended practices that are used **throughout the publishing industry**. Its activities include standards and best practices to guide the exchange between **publishers, librarians, technology providers and platforms, discovery systems, indices and catalogs**, and many other publishing and publishing-related providers.

Related Activities:

- NISO is active across numerous initiatives to convene interested stakeholders in a neutral, non-competitive environment to agree upon shared exchange formats and best practices.
- Recently, NISO convened the E-Book Bibliographic Metadata Requirements in the Sale, Publication, Discovery, and Preservation Supply Chain working group, which released a report for public comment in July – August 2020 and is currently finalizing its recommended practices. Their work includes many recommendations regarding key identifiers, metadata formats, distribution, and reporting, for suppliers throughout the ebooks supply chain.
- NISO has also led or is leading projects discussing alternative evaluation metrics for research (i.e., altmetrics), standardized usage harvesting (SUSHI) protocols, and Demand Driven Acquisition of Monographs. It has not previously convened an interest group or working group specific to OA monographs.

Operational and Technical Structure

- NISO's strategic standards work is overseen by our four leadership committees — an overarching Architecture Committee and three Topic Committees. The work of all four committees is aligned with NISO's strategic planning process, which is led by its Board. Committees are responsible for identifying, creating, and promoting standards and recommended practices.
- NISO does not itself develop technology directly, but provides documentation and community guidance on implementation. Committees and working groups are convened and run on a largely volunteer basis by interested members of the industry.

Key Principles

- NISO's mission is to build knowledge, foster discussion, and advance authoritative standards development through collaboration among the cultural, scholarly, scientific, and professional communities.
- As a standards organization, NISO aims for its activities to be highly inclusive.
- Though it supports OA-related activities, NISO is access model neutral.

C&E Analysis

NISO plays a unique role in the information industry by providing a forum for neutral and open discussion of shared solutions to common problems. Its activities are broad in nature, so nearly every organization in the scholarly communications and books supply chain will have some interaction with a NISO standard. NISO has a particularly strong presence in the scholarly publishing industry, where they have a long history of support for electronic publishing and library technical services (such as the SUSHI standard, which defines an automated usage harvesting protocol for COUNTER reports). Were they to get involved, NISO would be a valuable advocate for OAeBU efforts, and could provide a forum for discussion between stakeholders.

NISO would be less helpful in the actual implementation or maintenance of any infrastructure, however. As a standards body, its role is to help reach a shared definition of technical and other requirements, but it leaves the rest up to each individual provider. It is difficult to see NISO taking a more active role in handling transactions or data sharing between organizations, or in administering the data trust itself.

NISO is also not the only source for book and ebook standards (for example, the ONIX standard was jointly developed by EDItEUR, Book Industry Communication (BIC) in the UK, and the Book Industry Study Group (BISG) in the US). There may be some parts of the retail supply chain where NISO has a limited presence. However, its strength and relationships in the scholarly publishing ecosystem, along with its previous work in supporting the expanding role of OA, suggests NISO will be an important collaborator with OAeBU.

OA Switchboard

<https://www.oaswitchboard.org/>

Profile

The OA Switchboard is a central information exchange hub, connecting parties and systems, streamlining communication and the neutral exchange of OA related publication-level information, and ensuring a financial settlement can be done.

Legal Status

OA Switchboard is run by Stichting OA Switchboard, a foundation registered in the Netherlands.

Key Stakeholders:

- Focused on the **funder**, **institution**, and **academic publisher** communities.
- Additional support is provided by technology partners serving these workflows (e.g., manuscript submission systems).
- The OA Switchboard website provides a short list of early adopters and sponsors, who are involved in the MVP phase of development. The website also notes the support of Aries System as a Sponsor, and a strategic partnership with OASPA.

Related Activities:

- An OA Switchboard MVP was funded and developed in 2020, and enables publishers to send and receive pre-defined standardized messages from funders and institutions. These messages primarily are to do with eligibility for OA funding, and payment receipt and confirmation. The funding envisioned appears primarily to cover journal article publishing; if books were contemplated in the MVP it was not explicitly mentioned.
- The organization is now working in 2021 – 2022 on its “launch phase”, described as having a more solid basis, both in terms of functionality and service level, but also in operational adoption of funders, institutions and publishers.

Operational and Technical Structure

- The initial MVP project was funded via sponsors. OASPA then founded the independent Stichting OA Switchboard in October 2020 and established a new independent governing structure. The Steering Committee of the original switchboard are appointed as the first Board of Directors, with day-to-day management of the OA Switchboard to the Executive Director.
- Technology for the original MVP was provided by a third-party software development provider (ELITEX), selected via RFI in May 2020. It is unclear whether ELITEX is continuing their involvement in the “launch phase”.
- The OA Switchboard is working with participating publishers and technology providers to facilitate direct implementation of these capabilities.
- All solutions are developed on an open-source basis.

Key Principles

- Neutrality and independence.
- Collective control.
- Transparent cost structures.
- Facilitation of and compliance with OA funder mandates.

C&E Analysis

The OA Switchboard shares many of the same principles of the OAeBU project in terms of neutrality and independence. They have been successful in bringing together multiple stakeholders to pilot, prove, and invest in a shared infrastructure standard which can be further replicated by additional providers over time. They are open about the challenges of building this new standard despite the investments that larger publishers are making into their own homegrown, stand-alone systems. That they have also managed to do this while handling sensitive payments information is notable.

OA Switchboard is, however, focused on two key elements which do not align cleanly with the OA books monograph supply chain: they are so far developing the service to handle journals-specific metadata, and the central aim of the switchboard is to exchange payments information for funded OA articles. There is no current indication that the OA Switchboard would be interested in expanding upon its goals to collect usage information, and in fact platform providers (who are the progenitors of usage data) are conspicuously missing from their target participants. The direct applicability to OAeBU (monographs, usage information) would require a significant expansion of the OA Switchboard's current scope and stakeholders.

OpenAIRE Usage Statistics

<https://www.openaire.eu/usage-statistics/>

Profile

OpenAIRE is a European project supporting Open Science. It is both a network of dedicated Open Science experts promoting and providing training on Open Science, and also a technical infrastructure harvesting research output from connected data providers. OpenAIRE aims to establish an open and sustainable scholarly communication infrastructure responsible for the overall management, analysis, manipulation, provision, monitoring and cross-linking of all research outcomes.

Legal Status

OpenAIRE A.M.K.E. is a Non-Profit Partnership (NPP) incorporated under Greek law.

Key Stakeholders:

- Usage statistics services are part of the OpenAIRE Research Graph, which is intended as infrastructure to serve **funders, institutions, researchers, and publishers**.
- OpenAIRE is a participatory initiative with a focus on European Union institutions and scientific output

Related Activities:

- OpenAIRE's Usage Counts service contributes towards impact evaluation of usage activity in Open Access Repositories. The service collects usage data from participating Open Science content providers repositories, journals, and other scientific data sources, then aggregates them into standardized activity reports about research usage and uptake.
- Providers can push data to the service after registering with OpenAIRE, or arrange for data to be pulled using existing protocols like SUSHI-Lite or the IRUS-UK network. Statistics are generated using the COUNTER 4 code of practice.
- Information is then displayed in the OpenAIRE Research Graph. The graph service includes a de-duplication mechanism which aggregates and merges usage statistics which come from different sources, but relate to the same object.

Operational and Technical Structure

- OpenAIRE consists of a decentralized network of 34 National Open Access Desks (NAODs) in EU states and member countries, who act as project ambassadors and coordinators. OpenAIRE was incorporated as a standalone NPP in 2018.
- The Usage Statistics module relies on open source platforms (Matomo, Piwik Analytics) and is compliant with all EU privacy regulations. Hosting is provided by ICM of the University of Warsaw, with technical support provided by engineers and data scientists from participating institutions.

Key Principles

- The mission of OpenAIRE is to enact Open Science principles in European research (which includes OA publication models)
- Focus is on "implementation at all levels". This means it both offers services directly (such as the decentralized Research Graph), and provides a compliance framework for providers to promote interoperability

C&E Analysis

The goals of the OpenAIRE Usage Statistics align well with the objectives of OAeBU. Usage data is aggregated across multiple platforms and providers and combined with a de-duplicated index of open content. Some of these platforms are competitive with one another, underscoring the value of OpenAIRE as a neutral administrator. OpenAIRE has established agreements with each of its data sources, and allows multiple compliant routes for providers to contribute usage information. The providers themselves are diverse, and represent a range of stakeholders including publishers, aggregators, and institutional repositories.

OpenAIRE differs from OAeBU in two important ways: first, by focusing exclusively on content from the European Union, it does not overlap with the robust network of non-European OA monograph publishers and suppliers (such as American university presses). Secondly, OpenAIRE focuses on multiple content types, not exclusively OA monographs. This could affect the quality of its metadata handling for OA monographs: for example, its reporting is currently based on the COUNTER 4 standard, so reporting on books does not reflect the advances made in COUNTER 5 to improve comparisons of metrics across platforms. The latter is a tactical barrier and could be short term. In the long term, given the otherwise good alignment with the OAeBU initiative, OpenAIRE might benefit its stakeholders by applying OA monographs data trust best practices to other content types captured in its Research Graph.

Project COUNTER

<https://www.projectcounter.org/>

Profile

COUNTER provides the Code of Practice that enables publishers and vendors to report usage of their electronic resources in a consistent way. This enables libraries to compare data received from different publishers and vendors.

Legal Status

Project COUNTER is a not-for-profit company registered in England.

Key Stakeholders:

- COUNTER reporting is primarily intended for use by **librarians**, to help them demonstrate and assess the value of electronic collections.
- COUNTER supports those who serve librarians, such as **publishers, platforms, aggregators**, and other **technology providers**, by maintaining a shared Code of Practice which acts as a reporting standard.

Related Activities:

- COUNTER provides the Code of Practice that enables publishers and vendors to report usage of their electronic resources in a consistent way. The Code of Practice enables libraries to compare data received from different publishers and vendors. COUNTER will occasionally work with providers to update the Code of Practice to reflect the changing needs of the community.
- COUNTER maintains the Registries of Compliance which lists the publishers and vendors whose usage reporting has passed an independent audit. The registry also includes details of the content provider's SUSHI implementation (which allows automatic harvesting of COUNTER reports by library systems).
- COUNTER also provides advice and guidance to those implementing and using COUNTER statistics, such as a compliance checker tool.

Operational and Technical Structure

- COUNTER is supported by a global community of library, publisher and vendor members, who contribute to the development of the Code of Practice through working groups and outreach.
- COUNTER does not create any infrastructure centrally but does perform audits for compliance with the current Code of Practice.

Key Principles

- Aims to help librarians demonstrate the value of electronic resources.
- Facilitates the recording and reporting of online resource usage stats in a consistent and credible way.
- COUNTER Code of Practice has many accommodations for OA content, but does not promote one business model over another.

C&E Analysis

The COUNTER reporting format is widely followed across platforms serving the library market. Its regularity and ubiquity has even allowed for other standards to be built to automatically harvest and parse COUNTER-compliant data (such as the SUSHI standard developed by NISO). Several other multi-platform data-collection initiatives reviewed in this environmental scan, such as the IRUS Network, Knowledge Unlatched, and OpenAIRE Usage Statistics, follow the COUNTER format.

COUNTER also has a history of directly supporting similar initiatives to OAeBU: it was involved in Crossref's Distributed Usage Logging pilot, which aimed to collect and consolidate usage across platforms. In November 2020, Crossref voted to end its support of the Distributed Usage Logging project, leaving Project COUNTER's involvement unclear (the project has no successor owner).

When it comes to OA monographs, Project COUNTER's universe of stakeholders is narrower than that of OAeBU. Organizationally, Project COUNTER focuses closely on the needs of librarians, and its code of practice is not intended to capture usage outside of an institution. The COUNTER standard does not capture usage outside of institutional accounts – this is problematic for OA resources as such resources, by definition, do not require access control and hence much usage cannot be affiliated with specific institutions. COUNTER is similarly not concerned with consumer (i.e., retail) channels.

Project COUNTER also does not engage in any data collection of its own – like NISO, another standards organization, its focus is on providing guidance and creating a forum for discussion, not on implementation. This suggests that Project COUNTER is a valuable stakeholder for OAeBU to engage, and could be instrumental in solving mutual problems in capturing usage across platforms, but it appears unlikely Project COUNTER would provide direct support for administration or hosting the data trust.

4.2 Other Potential Collaborators

OAPEN Foundation

<https://oapen.org/>

Profile

OAPEN promotes and supports the transition to open access for academic books by providing open infrastructure services. It works with publishers to build a curated collection of OA books and provide services for publishers, libraries, and research funders, including hosting, depositing, quality assurance, dissemination, and digital preservation of OA monographs.

Legal Status

The OAPEN Foundation is a not for profit based in the Netherlands.

Key Stakeholders:

- The primary audience for OAPEN services is **publishers** of open access books.
- To provide a useful service OAPEN also engages with **end users, funders, discovery service providers**, and other compatible initiatives within scholarly publishing.
- Funding of the project was based on dissemination of OA monographs in Europe but "today its reach and activities are global."

Related Activities:

- OAPEN plays multiple roles in the supply chain for OA monographs: they are a platform provider, an index, and they provide toolkits and resources for authors considering publishing OA monographs.
- The OAPEN Library is the OAPEN Foundation's hosting platform for OA monographs. It contains more than 15,000 fully OA titles, from 300 publishers. Publishers can enter agreements with OAPEN and pay a modest fee for distribution. The OAPEN Library then provides increased discoverability for content by sending regular metadata fields to downstream consumers and discovery services. OAPEN also works with the IRUS network to provide COUNTER-compliant reporting for titles hosted on its platform.
- In partnership with OpenEdition, OAPEN also manages the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), which is an index of peer reviewed open access books published under an open license. DOAB indexes almost 40,000 books from over 600 publishers.

Operational and Technical Structure

- OAPEN was originally developed as a 30-month targeted project co-funded by the EU in its eContentplus-program from 2008 – 2010. Following the conclusion of the project, OAPEN continued its activities as a foundation.
- It is supported through funding from the EU, library and publisher memberships, and was recently designated as the beneficiary of a funding round from the Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS).

- Activities such as OAPEN Library and the DOAB are built by the OAPEN Foundation team on open-source software. Metadata feeds and reporting all follows industry standards (MARC XML, KBART, COUNTER, etc.)

Key Principles

- Achieve a sustainable OA publication model for academic books in humanities and social sciences.
- Improve the visibility and usability of high-quality academic research in Europe.

C&E Analysis

The OAPEN Foundation stands out as one of the few organizations to be fully dedicated to the support and maintenance of OA monographs. They have amassed a wide network of OA monograph publishers of all sizes and have built platforms and services to distribute metadata to important downstream suppliers – library discovery services, search engines, and other conduits for discovery by end users. In research interviews with C&E for our supply chain analysis, they described efforts to establish new and consistent best practices for OA books among the publishers they serve. They are involved in many development initiatives for OA monographs, including OAeBU.

The OAPEN Foundation at first glance appears well positioned to act as a central conduit for OA monographs usage data. In collaboration with OpenEdition, it operates the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), which indexes peer-reviewed OA monographs from multiple competing platforms. It has connections to key sources of title-level metadata, the aptitude to disambiguate and normalize that metadata, and could conceivably use these pipelines to collect usage data.

The OAPEN Foundation's other key product, the OAPEN Library, is a hosting platform (and therefore a source of usage), which competes for usage with other hosting platforms and aggregators in the market. Given the importance of the OAPEN Library as a distribution channel for OA monograph providers, OAPEN Foundation's most important role in a cross-industry data exchange is as a contributor of usage data from the OAPEN Library. While they have navigated this competitive / cooperative dynamic perfectly well in creating the DOAB, we nevertheless note it is a theoretical barrier to OAPEN's ability to serve as the *neutral* administrator of a data trust like OAeBU.

Sustainable History Monograph Pilot (SHMP)

<https://longleafservices.org/blog/the-sustainable-history-monograph-pilot/>

Profile

The Sustainable History Monograph Pilot (SHMP) is a Mellon-funded initiative to publish open digital editions of high-quality books from university presses in the field of history. Unlike many other Open Access (OA) pilots, SHMP transforms the publishing process and outputs, while focusing on a single academic discipline.

Legal Status

SHMP is a three-year Mellon-funded initiative led by the University of North Carolina Press and utilizing its subsidiary, Longleaf Services.

Key Stakeholders:

- The SHMP pilot is focused on **university press** titles publishing in the field of history. Its scope is to examine infrastructure needs for **publishers, distributors**, and other stakeholders in metadata and content exchange.

Related Activities:

- SHMP supports the OA publication of a selected title early in its life cycle. The participating university press is responsible for acquisition of the manuscript, peer review, and finalization of the content. Production (including copyediting, typesetting, and file creation) is handled by Longleaf Services, who then distributes the ebooks on an OA basis. Presses are supplied a print-ready PDF to produce print copies if they so choose.
- After publishing the new OA monograph, Longleaf Services then provides the press with qualitative and quantitative information about title performance. This performance data is gathered through manual collection and normalization of reports by Longleaf Services on behalf of participating publishers. Publishers are also asked to supply print sales data to help pilot participants assess the impact of OA publication on print sales.

Operational and Technical Structure

- The SHMP pilot is funded for three years through its original Mellon grant. That funding goes towards subsidizing the services and administration of the pilot handled by UNC Press and Longleaf Services, and small grants to participating presses for the acquisition costs of eligible monographs. The funding will cover 75 titles, across 23 participating university presses.
- Administration of the pilot does not appear to involve development of any new community or proprietary technology. The support provided by Longleaf Services appears to be provided by its existing staff and leadership.

Key Principles

- Defining consistent and reproducible publishing processes and outputs
- Development of sustainable OA monographs business models
- Focus on content within a single discipline (history)

C&E Analysis

The SHMP pilot is one of many involving the funding and creation of OA monographs, but it is unique for several reasons: first, it publishes titles only in a specific discipline (history), making this a more focused experiment on the impacts of OA publishing. Second, the pilot seeks to define better workflows and processes from the very first stages of the publishing process – these titles are truly “born OA”. This requires the support not just of the publisher, but of the service providers and distributors responsible for handling that title and bringing it to market. This provides some similarity with OAeBU: both seek to align the data and infrastructure needed to support OA monographs. It is notable that, for SHMP titles, Longleaf Services is also collecting usage information and providing analysis for its participating presses.

Assuming the SHMP pilot is successful, however, the outcomes of the two projects are very different. Where OAeBU envisions a collaborative data exchange administered by a neutral party, the SHMP initiative is based on a distributor – Longleaf Services – to take responsibility for usage data collection. (Interestingly, we see that the other born-OA distributor reviewed in this environmental scan, Knowledge Unlatched, already considers usage consolidation and reporting as part of its purview.) Should Longleaf Services continue to administer usage reporting collection as a service to its clients outside of the bounds of the SHMP pilot, this service would be competitive (albeit in a narrow sense) to the more open data exchange envisioned by OAeBU.

4.3 Potential Competitors

Knowledge Unlatched Open Analytics

<https://www.knowledgeunlatched.org/>

Profile

An Open Access service provider which initially offered an OA crowdfunding model to “unlatch” book and journal content, Knowledge Unlatched (KU) has since expanded into additional services to promote OA uptake and discovery.

Legal Status

Private for-profit.

Key Stakeholders:

- Knowledge Unlatched (KU) Open Analytics is primarily targeted at **publishers** of OA monographs, by offering distribution and management of OA titles.
- KU also serves **publishers, libraries, and funders** by coordinating and administering payment for OA publication (including through its OABle service, a competitor to the OA Switchboard).
- KU lastly offers its own OA platform which helps **publishers** provide content to **end users**. Their platform offers cataloging records and support for discovery via **third-party indices** (like MARC records for librarians to use in their ILS/LMS, KBART files for integration into KnowledgeBases, etc.).

Related Activities:

- The *KU Open Analytics* usage reporting tool consolidates usage from over 17 hosting platforms for OA books, including the OAPEN Library, JSTOR, Project MUSE, Bibliolabs, and Fulcrum.
- Usage data is aggregated for OA titles and presented in one place, to help publishers analyze the impact of OA marketing campaigns, carry out gap analysis, and support editorial decision-making. Reporting is available to provide to authors and funders in PDF format.
- *KU Open Analytics* is offered as a service to publishers, with pricing set by the number of platforms integrated into the dashboard.
- Though the service is primarily targeted at books that have been made OA through the KU funding program, all OA monographs are eligible for inclusion.

Operational and Technical Structure

- KU’s leadership team is comprised of an executive team, publisher relations, technologists, and library sales personnel.

- KU Open Analytics operates as a service, not a community initiative. Any technology developed in service of the analytics dashboard is proprietary to KU. According to interviews conducted with C&E, usage is collected directly by KU on behalf of publisher partners for incorporation into each dashboard.

Key Principles

- Sustainable and global Open Access: “Our vision is a sustainable market where scholarly books and journals are freely accessible for each and every reader around the world.”
- KU has received a B Corps certification from the global nonprofit B Lab (<https://bcorporation.eu/about-b-corps>). B Corps certification is a designation of social and environmental performance, transparency, and legal accountability of for-profit companies.

C&E Analysis:

The dashboard offered by *Knowledge Unlatched Open Analytics* is notably similar to the cross-platform usage analysis envisioned by the OAeBU project. The goals are also broadly the same: to allow publishers to monitor their usage across several platforms. Knowledge Unlatched has also succeeded in gathering this data from platforms which compete with one another, as OAeBU aims to do.

From a product development standpoint, Knowledge Unlatched’s offer of a cross-platform usage dashboard makes strategic sense for them: they offer services throughout the OA monographs distribution supply chain, from securing funding, content distribution, hosting, and discovery. Usage reporting and performance metrics are the next natural step on the value chain for these services.

However, unlike OAeBU, Knowledge Unlatched is not addressing this need through an open, community-driven data trust, but rather by positioning themselves at the center of a proprietary service. This provides a disincentive for Knowledge Unlatched to support a data trust if administered by another party, which would likely erode the value of its own services. Knowledge Unlatched Open Analytics is the most direct competitor to the OAeBU data exchange.

4.4 Narrower Collaboration Opportunities

IRUS Network

<https://irus.jisc.ac.uk/>

Profile

IRUS is a service which supports institutional repositories to provide COUNTER-conformant usage statistics for all content downloaded from participating institutional repositories. The IRUS Network encompasses other regional networks in the United Kingdom, United States, and Australia/New Zealand, as well as participating platforms.

Legal Status

The IRUS Network is a community-driven development managed by Jisc (a UK not-for-profit) and Cranfield University with support from Evidence Base.

Key Stakeholders:

- The IRUS Network comprises of primarily **institutional repositories, library publishers, and OA platforms**.
- Reports can be used to demonstrate value to **parent institutions and researchers**.
- Most members in the IRUS Network operate within regional hubs. JISC administers the IRUS-UK network and offers support to IRs in the US and Australia/New Zealand, through partnerships with local consortia (LYRASIS and CAVAL, respectively), and to the CORE and OAPEN Library platforms.

Related Activities:

- JISC launched IRUS-UK in 2012, as the implementation of the recommendations from its PIRUS2 project. The goal of the PIRUS2 project³ was to create a common standard for measuring online usage of individual articles for publishers and institutional repositories and to allow comparison of usage across platforms. PIRUS2 also envisioned a central clearinghouse (CCH) of article data (a role played for the IRUS Network by JISC).
- The IRUS service consolidates COUNTER-compliant statistics and benchmarking for institutional repositories, with the goal to help repositories develop policies and initiatives to support their objectives. The network also acts as an intermediary between UK repositories and other agencies.
- The IRUS Network has created a standard “tracker protocol”, which each repository is responsible for implementing. The tracker protocol (“a small piece of code”) allows JISC to collect the raw data and process into COUNTER-compliant reports.

³ A full description of the goals, outcomes, and recommendations from the PIRUS2 project can be found here: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1087/20110405>

- Statistics are then aggregated into openly available statistical reports, so that institutions can share usage information with individual researchers, administrators, peer institutions, and to review national trends.

Operational and Technical Structure

- The IRUS network is a service of JISC. There does not appear to be independent, separate governance of the IRUS Network. Each participant is individually responsible for implementing the standard created by the IRUS Network. JISC both collects and reports on the data collected from the network.

Key Principles

- Community driven, with development driven by user needs.
- Quantifying and demonstrating the value of institutional repositories to parent institutions and other stakeholders.
- All IRUS Network members provide only OA content.

C&E Analysis

PIRUS2, the progenitor of the IRUS Network which concluded in 2011, shared many similarities with the goals of the OAeBU initiative: its aim was to address the challenges of consolidating usage data from multiple stakeholders involved in the production and distribution of journals content. In the original pilot, stakeholders included both institutional repositories hosting the author’s accepted manuscript or a “green OA” copy, as well as publisher platforms hosting the final version of record. The implementation of the IRUS Network was seen as a successful outcome of the PIRUS2 project, although the implementation was ultimately limited to institutional repositories (hence the dropped “P”, for “publisher”).

This history could be a useful case study for OAeBU. The IRUS Network as it exists today differs from the goals of OAeBU for its narrower focus on a particular type of stakeholder. IRUS serves institutional repositories, which are one provider in the OA books supply chain, but which do not typically follow the same metadata distribution standards and relationships as other platforms within the supply chain – such as ebook aggregators, publisher platform providers, and retail ebook platforms.

Despite its limited reach into the broader universe of “traditional” suppliers, OAeBU may find it valuable to open a collaborative dialogue with the IRUS Network as a representative of institutional repositories’ interests, and a potential intermediary for gathering usage data from OA monographs (and potentially other content types stored within participating repositories) from their broad and diffuse network.

Repository Analytics and Metrics Portal (RAMP)

<https://rampanalytics.org/>

Profile

RAMP provides measurement and tracking for institutional repository materials that have surfaced in Google search results, and aggregates this data across more than 60 institutional repositories.

Legal Status

RAMP was developed by Montana State University, The University of New Mexico, OCLC Research, and Association of Research Libraries, with funding from the Institute of Museum and Library Services. RAMP is currently administered by Montana State University Library and The University of New Mexico Libraries.

Key Stakeholders:

- RAMP's primary stakeholders are administrators of **institutional repositories**, and those they serve (such as **authors, researchers and end users, institutions, and research funders**).

Related Activities:

- Institutional repositories can register with RAMP, at which point they will receive their own visualization dashboard. Currently over 60 repositories are registered, from multiple countries.
- RAMP data include the number of times an item appears in search results, the item's position in the search results, the number of times an item URL is clicked, click-through ratios, and information about where the search originated (date, device, and country).
- Metrics collected by RAMP are intended to demonstrate the utility of the institutional repository and track performance. It can also be used to measure the findability of the repository on the web, and diagnose discoverability problems.

Operational and Technical Structure

- RAMP is a community effort administered by a consortium of universities. We did not see evidence of a formal leadership structure or hierarchy, outside of its administration at Montana State University and University of New Mexico Libraries.
- Resources are built on open-source software and are offered as a service to support the library community. Its operators occasionally publish the project's code, data outputs, and other documentation in Github, Dryad (a data deposit service), and Zenodo.

Key Principles

- Aim is to demonstrate usage and value of institutional repositories.
- Data collected by RAMP is made publicly available for community use.

C&E Analysis

RAMP, like several others reviewed in this environmental scan, focuses primarily on measuring content hosted on institutional repositories. RAMP is unique in measuring usage not in a COUNTER-compliant format, but based on web-scale search results and discoverability.

The COUNTER code of practice has several shortcomings when it comes to accurately measuring usage for open access content, stemming from the standard's intended use for reporting to libraries (and not publishers). RAMP provides an example of an alternative reporting scheme which allows for more open discovery from non-library platforms and search engines (an incredibly important source of traffic for OA monographs). Its approach could be instructive in capturing the metrics of value which matter to platforms catering directly to the researcher, and to the institutions which fund those open platforms.

At the same time, RAMP shows no signs of engagement with other types of platforms beyond institutional repositories, which makes its core audience narrower than that of OAeBU. Given the alignment of interests, RAMP poses a potential collaboration opportunity to build relationships and potentially a tailored set of best practices to integrate its participating repositories into the data trust.

Toward an Open Monograph Ecosystem (TOME)

<https://www.openmonographs.org/>

Profile

The initiative is focused on universities and university presses, as a way to explore the sustainability of OA monographs.

Legal Status

TOME launched in 2017 as a five-year pilot project of the Association of American Universities (AAU), Association of Research Libraries (ARL), and Association of University Presses (AUPresses). At the end of the five-year pilot in 2022, the project partners will assess the outcomes of the initiative, and then a decision will be made about next steps.

Key Stakeholders:

- The TOME initiative is focused on exploring the sustainability of OA monographs for **universities** and **university presses**. There are currently 60 university presses participating.

Related Activities:

- Participating colleges and universities commit to providing baseline grants of \$15,000 to support the publication of open access monographs of 90,000 words or fewer (with additional funding for works of greater length or complexity).
- TOME publishers are required to distribute files of each book (PDF and ePUB3 where possible) to a number of OA repositories. These include OAPEN Library, HathiTrust Digital Library, and Knowledge Unlatched Open Research Library, JSTOR Books, and MUSE Open, the author's institutional repository, and the TOME repository (<https://tome.figshare.com/>)
- Leaders of the TOME initiative are manually collecting usage reports from each platform for titles published under the scheme, to monitor their performance and report on the overall initiative.⁴

Operational and Technical Structure

- TOME is guided by an Advisory Board made up of representatives from the Association of American Universities, the Association of Research Libraries, and the Association of University Presses. A Visiting Program Officer (VPO) is responsible for coordinating communications, tracking progress, and promoting participation in the TOME initiative by eligible authors.

⁴ As an example, see the most recent progress report from Virginia Tech, published on February 16, 2021: <https://blogs.lt.vt.edu/openvt/2021/02/16/tome-at-virginia-tech-a-progress-report/>

- Participating presses and their institutions are individually responsible for funding and publishing titles under the TOME program, following a set of best practices recommended by program leadership.
- In C&E’s research interview with the TOME VPO, Peter Potter, he indicated that the collection and collation of OA monograph usage reports is conducted manually, on an experimental basis. TOME’s intent does not appear to be the creation of any shareable technology outputs or infrastructure for the long-term collection of usage data.

Key Principles

- Defining consistent and reproducible processes.
- Development of sustainable OA monographs business models.
- Increase the presence and global readership of humanities and social science scholarship.

C&E Analysis

The TOME initiative brings together a diverse set of university presses, to create a better understanding of the tools and capabilities required for the publication of OA monographs. Its goal is to encourage institutions to commit funding for OA titles, and then to track their performance to build a shared definition of success across funders and publishers. TOME is aligned with OAeBU in its understanding of consolidated usage statistics as a key performance metric for OA monographs.

However, TOME’s primary focus is in ensuring a sustainable and robust funding system for digital monographs, through the awarding of grants for eligible titles. The books themselves are produced by the participating press under standard workflows (with non-standard interventions as needed to support the OA model). While this creates an incentive to improve the infrastructure around OA, TOME’s scope does not currently include developing this shared set of processes, standards and metadata elements. There is perhaps opportunity for OAeBU, if it chooses, to engage TOME participants as stakeholders in defining these standards and success metrics based on their initial experience in the pilot. As TOME participants typically have significant activity in more traditional forms of book publishing, this community would also be key stakeholders should the OAeBU data trust expand its purview to paid access as well as OA titles.

APPENDIX: Additional Brief Profiles

This appendix includes profiles of providers included in our environmental scan, which we found had more limited stakeholder overlap and applicability to the OAeBU initiative. They are included as there may be opportunities to learn from certain of these providers, but they are likely of lower priority for engagement by the OAeBU project team. The table below includes a list of these providers and potential areas of overlap (if any).

Provider	C&E Assessment of OAeBU Opportunity
Altmetric	Limited Stakeholder Overlap
COKI	Shared Stakeholders, Different Focus
EBSCO Panorama Analytics	Shared Stakeholders, Commercial Service
Ingram iQ	Shared Stakeholders, Commercial Service
Global Dataverse Community Consortium	Limited Stakeholder Overlap
Lens.org	Limited Stakeholder Overlap
Liblynx / PSI (OA Analytics)	Shared Stakeholders, Commercial Service
Make Data Count	Limited Stakeholder Overlap
MUSE Open	Shared Stakeholders, Commercial Service
My Science Work	Limited Stakeholder Overlap
Open Syllabus OER Metrics	Shared Stakeholders, Different Focus
Unizin	Shared Stakeholders, Different Focus

Altmetric	
URL	https://www.altmetric.com
Profile	“Altmetrics” are metrics and qualitative data that complement traditional, citation-based metrics. Altmetric is a service which captures and collates these metrics to provide insight about how research is being used and discussed around the world.
Legal Status	Part of the Digital Science portfolio of companies, owned by Holtzbrinck, a private for-profit.
Key Stakeholders	Publishers, institutions, researchers, research funders.
Related Activities	Altmetric has created a database which captures “attention data” for scholarly outputs. Attention is measured from multiple sources, including open peer reviews, public policy documents, research blogs, media coverage, bookmarks on reference managers like Mendeley, and social media (e.g., Twitter). The database is accessible via Altmetric Explore, its dashboard product, and Altmetric Badges which publishers can embed alongside their articles. Altmetric also offers an API for further integrations. Books data is available as part of the Altmetric Explorer as an optional add-on.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	Altmetric was founded in 2011 by Euan Edie and began receiving support from Digital Science in 2012. Startups in the Digital Science portfolio are primarily tech companies with a focus on scholarly publishing and academic research, who receive investment and access to industry knowledge and skillsets. Altmetric services also rely on community infrastructure, such as Crossref DOIs, to track individual research outputs.
Key Principles	Altmetric aims to "Provide a more complete view of research impact."
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Like OAeBU, Altmetric aims to collate data about a piece of research from multiple competing sources, to provide interested stakeholders a view into their performance. • This is a journal-focused service, which captures usage only on the publisher’s platform, and relies heavily on the DOI. While there is some (optional) support for books, Altmetric admits some limitations into their ability to track titles. This reduces the competitive nature of Altmetric and OAeBU, as the two services currently seek to address two different types of audience.

COKI	
URL	https://openknowledge.community/about-coki/
Profile	Founded at Curtin University by project leads Professor Cameron Neylon and Professor Lucy Montgomery, the COKI project has used big data and cloud computing approaches to create the world's leading data set relating to scholarly communication, open access, diversity and inclusion.
Legal Status	Strategic initiative of Curtin University.
Key Stakeholders	Higher Education Institutions, research funders, and stakeholders in supporting their research outputs (e.g., publishers).
Related Activities	<p>COKI has amassed a database of over 12 trillion data points on research output and other metrics (such as DEI). Its output includes two openly accessible dashboards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The COKI Research Dashboard provides data about research funding, based on acknowledgements in research articles • The COKI Open Access Dashboard provides a view of the volume of research output on a country by country basis, including what portion of that research is published Open Access.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	The COKI project operates out of Curtin University, which has also provided strategic research funding and in-kind support. Other funding has come in from Arcadia and the Andrew W Mellon Foundation. The project website reports the COKI team is exploring additional funding to move from a startup to a sustainable organization.
Key Principles	“The Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative aims to play a leading role in analyzing and reporting on the way higher education institutions provide open access to knowledge and opportunity.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAeBU shares many synergies with the COKI project, not least being its overlap in participants. • The projects are nevertheless different in scope: COKI focuses on HEI as its primary audience, and combines openly-available data, whereas the OAeBU data trust envisions more direct collaboration between stakeholders.

EBSCO Panorama Analytics	
URL	https://www.ebsco.com/products/panorama
Profile	EBSCO's Panorama Analytics service allows libraries to collect, manipulate, and analyze data across multiple systems to support collection and program related decisions
Legal Status	EBSCO is a privately-held for-profit company.
Key Stakeholders	Libraries and Information Managers.
Related Activities	Panorama, launched in March 2021, allows libraries to automate data collection from multiple systems including the ILS, COUNTER reports, and student information systems, in order to make evidence-based decisions. Participating libraries receive a self-serve platform with visualization tools and custom set up to collect data from each of their pertinent systems. Panorama Analytics is part of a suite of collection development services offered by EBSCO, including Usage Consolidation (a service which captures a library's usage across platforms) and book/ebook acquisition profiles (through their GOBI Library Services division).
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	EBSCO is a leading subscription services vendor and aggregator with a strong presence in libraries worldwide. Panorama is their newest collection development product and was launched with a small number of pilot institutions. Those pilot institutions provided data, feedback on the dashboards, and assisted with constructing data pipelines from third party systems.
Key Principles	"EBSCO created <i>Panorama</i> not only to improve the workflow processes for academic libraries, but to provide them with real-time insights on collections and services to make evidence-based decisions and reinforce the library's value to the institution."
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBSCO's services are designed to help libraries combine and collate usage and other data into one platform, to help libraries assess the value of their content purchases (including monographs). • This function differs from that of OAeBU in that the data is intended to serve the library, not the publisher, and the focus is correspondingly on paid-access content, not OA.

Ingram IQ	
URL	https://www.ingramcontent.com
Profile	Ingram IQ is a reporting and analytics publisher portal for Ingram distribution clients.
Legal Status	Private, for-profit.
Key Stakeholders	Publishers.
Related Activities	Ingram IQ customers receive self-serve reporting on sales data about their titles, including views across “related product” (e.g., the softcover and hardcover version, or the print and digital version of the same title). Reports are available at the channel level, allowing publishers to see sales activity through each of their retail and library-focused sales routes. Publisher pricing for each account is based on that publisher’s prior year sales. All publishers with Ingram distribution agreements are required to maintain an active iQ account.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	Ingram is one of the largest book distribution companies and, following the closure of Baker & Taylor’s wholesale business, the only book wholesaler in the US. They offer print and digital distribution, print-on-demand, and digital asset management to publishers in several markets.
Key Principles	“Dedicated to Serving the Book Industry. Experience and services to get more books into the hands of more readers.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ingram IQ provides an example of a service consolidating data across platforms and channels to provide publishers important business intelligence about a title. The company has relationships with many of the various publishers, platforms, retail channels, library channels, and standards organizations within the books industry, and is exploring future involvement with OA monographs (according to a research interview conducted with C&E in our supply chain analysis). • Ingram IQ is very much focused on the paid-access supply chain, unlike OAeBU. • As a distributor, Ingram offers the IQ dashboard as a paid service, not as a piece of community infrastructure. • While there is no evidence that Ingram would start to seek usage data along with sales data from its platform partners for use in Ingram IQ, if it did so the service would be competitive with OAeBU.

Global Database Community Consortium	
URL	http://dataversecommunity.global
Profile	Global Dataverse Community Consortium (GDCC) will provide international organization to existing community efforts and will provide a collaborative venue for institutions to leverage economies of scale in support of Dataverse repositories around the world.
Legal Status	Currently run out of Harvard University
Key Stakeholders	Institutional repositories in charge of managing data for an institution
Related Activities	The GDCC is an early-stage initiative designed to build best practices and organization for the collection of research data in institutional repositories. Services and activities include installation and consulting services, access to a GitHub repository with community contributions to the project, and access to a shared DataCite membership for issuing DOIs to research data sets. The cost to participate in the consortium is tied directly to the number of DOIs issued to each institution's repositories.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	There are currently three long standing community members serving on the initial "pilot phase" oversight committee, who are responsible for developing a more defined governance structure. Activities are conducted with open source software. DOIs are issued by DataCite, which specializes in DOIs for research data.
Key Principles	"Community driven". Goals for the consortium will be defined by the participants.
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The GDCC is still a nascent initiative, with a focus on stakeholders responsible for managing research datasets. • GDCC stakeholders have very little overlap with the OA monographs supply chain, with the possible exception those institutional repositories which store both data sets and books. This is a similar stakeholder group as served by the IRUS Network or RAMP, which both are more focused on usage and are therefore more likely to be fruitful collaborators for OAeBU.

Lens.Org	
URL	https://www.lens.org
Profile	Lens.org seeks to source, merge and link diverse open knowledge sets, including scholarly works and patents, to inform discovery, analysis, decision making, and collaboration between stakeholders.
Legal Status	Lens.org is a service of Cambia, an independent non-profit social enterprise.
Key Stakeholders	Research funders, policy makers, funders, patent offices, and publishers.
Related Activities	The Lens Citation Graph includes over 200 million scholarly records, compiled and harmonized from Microsoft Academic, PubMed and Crossref, enhanced with UnPaywall open access information, CORE full text, and links to ORCID. The goal is to trace the relationship between research findings and real world innovation and product development. Data is openly available at Lens.org, but the organization is also partnering with publishers like SPIE to integrate data directly into the publisher’s website.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	Lens.org was originally launched by Cambia as the Patent Lens before expanding its purview to scholarly literature. The project received grants from the Bill and Melina Gates Foundation, Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, Lemelson Foundation, Rockefeller Foundation, and the Wellcome Trust. Lens.org is cloud-based and infrastructure is open and public, with a small number of staff and developers listed on their website.
Key Principles	“The Lens has been committed to enabling innovation and making problem solving more inclusive, affordable, and transparent.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lens.org is a very broad database of content, and the project may be notable to OAeBU for its work normalizing data across sources to tie research outputs to real-world outcomes. • Both initiatives are aimed at improving decision-making for research funders. • Currently, Lens does not appear to be gathering any usage-related data for OA monographs, or any other content types. Most of its metadata comes from other third-party indices, not the publishers or platforms who are the most appropriate source for usage data.

LibLynx / PSI (OA Analytics)	
URL	https://www.liblynx.com
Profile	LibLynx’s primary product is Connect, which is an API-based solution for managing user authentication and authorizations. LibLynx also has a partnership with PLoS to develop OA Analytics, using PSI’s IP registry.
Legal Status	For-profit / LLC.
Key Stakeholders	Target users are libraries and publishers, via integration with platform providers.
Related Activities	LibLynx and PLoS have partnered to develop new OA metrics for PLoS content, which use PSI’s IP registry to improve reporting capabilities for OA articles. This is a pilot initiative which is designed to establish new best practices, which can be offered to additional publishers in future.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	LibLynx was founded by Tim Lloyd (CEO) and Paul Dixon (CTO). It has a small team of technologists, and a history of collaboration with other organizations.
Key Principles	LibLynx focuses on making flexible and customizable authentication technology and solutions.
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LibLynx and PSI’s work with PLoS on improved OA Analytics aims to address many of the shortcomings of COUNTER, a shared pain point across all OA content. What they learn in these efforts could be educative for the data trust in defining best practices for OA usage and assessment. • LibLynx is ultimately offering a service – not a community initiative – which is the primary distinction with the aims and scope of OAeBU.

Make Data Count	
URL	https://makedatacount.org
Profile	Make Data Count is a global, community-led initiative focused on the development of open research data assessment metrics
Legal Status	“Make Data Count” is part of a broader Research Data Alliance (RDA) Data Usage Metrics Working Group. The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Foundation is a non-profit charitable organization registered as a legal entity in the UK
Key Stakeholders	Funders, data repositories, infrastructure providers (like Crossref), and publishers
Related Activities	The MDC initiative is currently focused on three primary goals: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased adoption of standardized data usage across repositories through enhanced processing and reporting services 2. Increased implementations of proper data citation practices at publishers by working in conjunction with publisher advocacy groups and societies 3. Promotion of bibliometrics and qualitative and quantitative studies around data usage and citation behaviors
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	Make Data Count is driven by project partners at California Digital Library, Crossref, DataCite, DataONE, ScholCommLab, University of Ottawa, and ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics. It has received funding from National Science Foundation, Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, and Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. MDC is a largely volunteer-led and not focused on direct implementation, but rather the promotion of certain best practices by providers.
Key Principles	“To produce evidence-based studies on researcher behavior in citing and using data, as well as drive a community of practice around open, normalized data usage and data citation as initial steps towards the development of research data assessment metrics.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Make Data Count initiative is an excellent example of community promotion of standards and best practices among a wide group of stakeholders, with similar tactics to those of OAeBU. • The participants in the Make Data Count initiative are focused on the initial creation of distribution and discovery infrastructure for research datasets. Make Data Count’s providers and participants show little overlap with stakeholders in OA monograph distribution and usage collection, which suggests its standards will evolve separately than those underpinning OAeBU.

MUSE Open	
URL	https://muse.jhu.edu
Profile	Project MUSE is an aggregator platform which hosts and distributes scholarly journals and books in the humanities and social sciences published by University Press partners
Legal Status	Project MUSE is a division of the Johns Hopkins University Press, part of Johns Hopkins University
Key Stakeholders	University Presses, libraries
Related Activities	In 2016, Project MUSE grant from the Mellon Foundation for MUSE Open, which aimed to allow Project MUSE to distribute selected OA books in browser-native HTML5 format, with enhanced functionality.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	The initial Mellon grant helped Project MUSE develop the technical infrastructure to support OA monographs. MUSE Open is now part of the same platform as the Project MUSE paid-access aggregation service, and continues to distribute OA content for participating university presses.
Key Principles	“Our goal is to ensure that Open Access (OA) monographs are visible, discoverable, and potentially transformative in a highly diversified platform environment.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project MUSE is one of many platforms which could serve as a source of usage for the data trust. • Project MUSE competes with other sources of usage data (such as the JSTOR, EBSCO, and ProQuest aggregator platforms), which may prevent it from offering a consolidated dashboard view of cross-platform usage – either independently or as an administrator of the OAeBU data trust.

My Science Work	
URL	https://www.mysciencework.com/sirius
Profile	MyScienceWork serves the international scientific community and promotes easy access to scientific publications, unrestricted diffusion of knowledge and open science. Their comprehensive database includes more than 90 million scientific publications and 12 million patents.
Legal Status	Ltd. Company, incorporated in Luxembourg
Key Stakeholders	Scientists, institutions (including providers of institutional repositories), and publishers
Related Activities	My Science Work is the creator of the Sirius database, which indexes over 568 data sources (including open repositories, publisher databases, and third parties such as ORCID, Crossref, and citation databases). Sirius then uses text mining and natural-language processing to map relations between stakeholders and research outputs.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	My Science Work was founded as a technology startup in 2010, and now has dedicated teams based in the US, Luxembourg, and France.
Key Principles	“Our vision for the near future is to empower research institutions and industries with more intelligence related to research fields by aggregating all available data related to research results to accelerate findings, optimize funding and research efforts, improve transparency, bridge the knowledge gap between academia and industry and avoid duplicate research.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My Science Work has created a robust bibliometric database, and they stand out for their ability to link data across multiple sources. Because OAeBU will also require books to be identified across platforms using different identifiers, My Science Work’s methods could be educative. • Data sources for the Sirius database do not include direct feeds from publishers or platforms, which are the most comprehensive source of usage data. My Science Work would need to expand its current stakeholders and partners to serve as a central source for usage data.

Open Syllabus OER Metrics	
URL	https://oer.opensyllabus.org
Profile	OER Metrics tracks the adoption of openly licensed textbooks and monographs in higher education, using licensing information from the Open Textbook Library and the Directory of Open Access Books.
Legal Status	501(c)(3)
Key Stakeholders	Instructors/faculty, publishers, and institutions
Related Activities	The goal of the Open Syllabus Project is to help quantify the utility of certain titles in the classroom (as measured by the number of adoptions). It has amassed a database of OER adoptions mostly through crawling publicly accessible university websites. The Explorer currently displays the roughly 6 million syllabi collected through 2017.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	Joe Karaganis is the Director, supported by a small technical staff. It also has a Board and an Advisory Group, and a list of funders as well which provide the financial backing for the project. There does not appear to be a business model at this time.
Key Principles	“The Open Syllabus helps instructors develop classes, libraries manage collections, and presses develop books. It supports students and lifelong learners in their exploration of topics and fields. It creates incentives for faculty to improve teaching materials and to use open licenses. It supports work on aligning higher education with job market needs and on making student mobility easier. It also challenges faculty and universities to work together to steward this important data resource.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAeBU and the Open Syllabus project share some overlap in stakeholders, but OER Metrics is focused on the utility of these books as textbooks, not the overall usage of the titles. • The Open Syllabus project gathers its data through crawling openly available datasets and envisions a suite of additional services based on faculty-contributed resources. It is not currently positioned to receive direct feeds of usage information from OER platforms or publishers. • Given the shared mission to support OA books, but the differing approaches to getting there, OER Metrics appears more synergistic to OAeBU than it is competitive.

Unizin	
URL	www.unizin.org
Profile	Founded in 2015, Unizin is a membership-based organization of higher ed institutions which develops technology to help its members enable better use of digital content and data and improve pedagogy. Unizin’s 25 member institutions serve over 915,000 students.
Legal Status	501(c)(3) registered in Delaware.
Key Stakeholders	Higher education institutions, students.
Related Activities	The Unizin Data Platform is a Platform-as-a-Service solution that collects and standardizes data from a variety of sources (including Student Information Systems and Learning Management Systems) to simplify data management and save member institutions time and effort. Its goal is to gather the broadest collection of anonymized learner data in higher education. Unizin also offers a Marketplace, where institutions and faculty can manage selection and adoption of OER, etexts, courseware, and other materials.
Operational and Technical Infrastructure	Unizin is a member-based organization of US universities supported by a small full-time staff. Representatives from member institutions serve on volunteer-led committees to develop key initiatives, such as affordable digital content (including OER), learning analytics, learning tools, libraries, and app development. It also partners with a number of tech providers and publishers, and works with them to establish common standards such as the Unizin Common Data Model and accessibility standards.
Key Principles	“Unizin enables higher education to meet the moment of digital transformation by developing and delivering solutions that address the pressing and complex challenges of data, analytics and digital content.”
C&E Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unizin is a small but innovative consortium of top-tier research institutions, and is notable for working directly and collaboratively with technology providers to enforce better standards and best practices (such as security and privacy in data sharing). • Though it does incorporate OER into its activities, its initiatives are more focused on education, with only moderate overlap with the books supply chain. Data from these institutions represents only a narrow slice of the universe of total usage.